

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПО КОНТРОЛЮ ЗАТРАТ В СИСТЕМЕ ЛОГИСТИКИ ЦЕПОЧКИ ПОСТАВОК

*Хуан Янь,
Кудрявцева О.*

*Харьковский национальный автомобильно-дорожный университет,
г. Харьков*

RESEARCH ON COST CONTROL OF SUPPLY CHAIN LOGISTICS SYSTEM

*Huang Yan,
Kudriavtseva O.*

*Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University
Kharkiv*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Логистические расходы обычно составляют большую долю от общей стоимости предприятия, но его сложная внутренняя структура и меняющаяся внешняя среда делают его сложной и трудно контролируемой областью. Особенно в контексте управления цепочками поставок, постепенно проникающего на все уровни предприятия, контроль логистических расходов является не только внутренней проблемой предприятия, но также включает сотрудничество и взаимодействие с партнерами по цепочке поставок. Поэтому в этой статье будет проведено углубленное исследование контроля логистических расходов предприятия с точки зрения цепочки поставок в надежде предоставить предприятиям эффективные стратегии и предложения по контролю затрат, а также дополнительно улучшить конкурентное преимущество предприятий в цепочке поставок.

ABSTRACT

Logistics costs usually account for a large proportion of the total cost of an enterprise, but its complex internal structure and changing external environment make it a complex and difficult to control field. Especially in the context of supply chain management gradually penetrating into all levels of the enterprise, the control of logistics costs is not only an internal issue of the enterprise, but also involves cooperation and collaboration with supply chain partners. Therefore, this paper will conduct an in-depth study of enterprise logistics cost control from the perspective of the supply chain, in the hope of providing enterprises with effective cost control strategies and suggestions, and further improving the competitive advantage of enterprises in the supply chain.

Ключевые слова: цепочка поставок; стоимость логистики; контроль затрат.

Keywords: supply chain; logistics cost; cost control.

INTRODUCTION

With the development of economic globalization and increasingly fierce market competition, enterprises are faced with the problem of how to effectively manage and optimize logistics and transportation costs in the process of pursuing efficiency and competitiveness. As an important part of enterprise supply chain management, logistics and transportation are no longer able to meet the development needs of enterprises under the background of diversified logistics demand and complicated transportation methods. It is urgent to carry out optimization management in a more systematic and scientific way. Logistics and transportation costs such as transportation costs, warehousing costs, packaging costs, and related management and service costs are directly related to the market price of enterprise products and the market competitiveness of enterprises. With the rapid development of information technology, the introduction of digital and automation technologies can improve the transparency and efficiency of logistics operations, further reduce costs through refined management, and provide new solutions for optimizing logis-

tics cost management. At present, scholars have conducted research on the management of logistics and transportation costs of enterprises. Mo Yifei (2024) examined logistics cost management from the perspective of the supply chain, and proposed logistics cost management strategies such as consolidating the supply chain, controlling procurement costs; developing smart supply, improving management efficiency; adjusting the human resource structure, and reducing labor costs. "; Wang Lingshu et al. (2023) proposed methods such as establishing advanced logistics cost concepts and improving the logistics management system to help small and medium-sized logistics companies improve profitability, increase customer loyalty, expand market share, and improve the transparency and responsiveness of the supply chain!; Li Jinxia (2016) pointed out that logistics cost optimization management has become an important influencing factor in market competition, and based on the theory of value chain management, proposed that enterprises should continuously optimize logistics cost management, improve traditional cost management models, flexibly apply value chain theory, give play to the barrel effect, and improve

the economic benefits of enterprises. "; Song Min (2015) pointed out that solving the dilemma of enterprise logistics cost management requires finding methods at both the institutional and technical levels, and the mechanism optimization work can be carried out from three aspects: introducing market mechanisms, establishing cost units, and enhancing business capabilities": Jiang Hongmei (2010) optimized logistics cost management through the information provided by the activity-based cost method, and adopted strategies such as logistics operation chain transformation, rational resource allocation, and logistics operation standardization to effectively control and reduce logistics costs. Yang Yan et al. (2010) constructed an innovative enterprise logistics cost management model based on the concept and method of value chain management. Therefore, this paper refers to relevant literature, analyzes the priority of optimizing the components of logistics transportation costs based on quantitative analysis, and proposes a series of scientific logistics cost

management optimization strategies, in order to provide theoretical reference for enterprises to improve the existing logistics cost management system.

1. Theoretical basis

1.1 Logistics and transportation costs

Logistics and transportation costs cover all costs from the purchase of goods to the destination, mainly including transportation costs, loading and unloading fees, warehousing fees, packaging fees, and related management fees and service fees, which directly affect the profitability and price competitiveness of enterprises. In modern enterprise operations, logistics and transportation cost management has become a complex supply chain optimization problem. Enterprises need to comprehensively consider measures such as optimizing routes, improving loading and unloading operations, using efficient packaging materials, and optimizing transportation methods to reduce logistics and transportation costs. The specific logistics and transportation costs are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Logistics and transportation costs

Cost Type	describe	Influencing factors
Shipping costs	Including fuel costs, vehicle maintenance costs, driver wages, etc.	Distance, mode of transport, fuel prices, road conditions
Loading and unloading charges	Includes labor and machinery costs for loading and unloading	Cargo types, loading and unloading efficiency, equipment usage
Storage Fees	Including warehouse rental fees, insurance premiums, cargo storage fees, etc.	Warehouse location, warehouse technology, storage time
Packaging fee	Including packaging material costs and packaging operation fees	Selection of packaging materials and packaging methods
Management and service fees	Includes costs for management activities and additional services related to logistics and transportation	Management level, service level, and application of information systems

1.2 The Importance of Logistics and Transportation Cost Management

In the global economic environment, transportation costs account for the bulk of the total logistics costs of enterprises. Through effective cost management, enterprises can improve their market competitiveness, provide more competitive prices while maintaining reasonable profits, attract more customers, thereby improving the efficiency of the enterprise supply chain, quickly responding to market changes, improving customer satisfaction, and promoting the long-term development of the enterprise. From the perspective of strategic management, good cost management can provide enterprises with greater strategic flexibility, enabling them to expand into new markets, adjust supply chain structures, or respond to economic cycle fluctuations when necessary. With the strengthening of environmental protection laws and regulations and the popularization of green consumption concepts, enterprises can also reduce environmental costs, promote corporate social responsibility, and enhance corporate brand image and consumer trust through green logistics practices.

1.3 Objectives of Logistics and Transportation Cost Management

Enterprise logistics and transportation cost management needs to balance the relationship between cost, time and service quality, optimize the enterprise's resource allocation, ensure that transportation activities

maximize transportation efficiency at the lowest cost, and thus support the overall profitability and market competitiveness of the enterprise. This requires enterprises to reduce direct transportation costs such as fuel costs and labor costs, control indirect costs such as storage fees, packaging material fees, loss fees and technology investment returns, and thus improve the price competitiveness of products or services, meet the ever-changing market demand, and improve customer satisfaction, and improve the responsiveness and flexibility of the supply chain. In addition, with the global attention to environmental issues and the rise of green logistics consumption trends, the goal of logistics cost management has gradually changed from simple cost reduction to comprehensive consideration of economic benefits and environmental impacts, by adopting environmentally friendly transportation methods and materials, optimizing cargo loading and transportation routes, reducing energy consumption and waste generation, so as to achieve a win-win situation of cost savings and environmental protection, and bring more policy benefits and market opportunities. The goal of logistics and transportation cost management is to drive enterprises towards a more efficient, economical and sustainable direction through comprehensive and multi-angle strategies.

1.4 Development of China’s logistics economy

With the rapid development of China's economy, the logistics industry has become an important part of the national economy. In recent years, the market size of my country's logistics industry has continued to expand, but it also faces cost pressure and efficiency challenges. As shown in Table 1, according to statistics from the National Development and Reform Commission, the total social logistics costs increased steadily from 2017 to 2023 , especially the growth in 2021 and 2023 is more significant.

The data shows that transportation costs dominate the entire logistics costs, and this trend is obvious in

each year. The proportion of logistics costs to GDP has increased year by year, from 14.74% in 2017 to 16.41% in 2023, showing that the proportion of logistics costs in the national economy has gradually increased, and logistics costs have become an increasingly heavy cost burden that all types of companies must face. The situation of efficiency and cost control is not optimistic. Although the growth of logistics costs reflects the active development of the industry, it also shows the challenges faced by the logistics industry in cost control and improving operational efficiency.

Table 2

Statistics on the growth rate of China's logistics costs and its proportion of GDP from 2017 to 2023

years	Total logistics costs (trillion yuan)	Logistics cost growth rate (%)	GDP (Trillion RMB)	Logistics costs as a percentage of GDP (%)	Shipping costs (Trillion RMB)	Custody fees (Trillion RMB)	Management Fees (Trillion RMB)
2017	12.1	--	82.08	14.74	6.6	3.9	1.6
2018	13.1	9.92	90.03	14.77	6.9	4.6	1.8
2019	14.6	9.77	98.65	14.80	7.7	5.0	1.9
2020	14.9	2.05	101.60	14.67	7.8	5.1	1.9
2021	16.7	12.08	105.00	15.90	9.0	5.6	2.2
2022	17.8	6.59	108.50	16.41	9.55	5.59	2.26
2023	19.1	7.03	110.32	17.52	9.93	6.32	2.57

Data source: National Development and Reform Commission and China Federation of Logistics and Purchasing, "National Logistics Operation Report" (2017-2023).

In recent years, my country has taken many positive measures to reduce costs in the logistics industry in terms of policy support, technology introduction, and standard setting. Especially in terms of policy support, by optimizing government service processes and promoting support policies such as simplifying transportation and logistics certificates, reducing fees, improving quality and increasing efficiency, the logistics industry reduced logistics costs by more than 130 billion yuan in 2020, effectively reducing the burden on real economy enterprises and improving the overall operating efficiency of the logistics industry.

2. Construction and analysis of logistics cost indicator system,

2.1 Selection of core indicators

Logistics costs are all the expenses incurred by an enterprise in its logistics activities. To accurately measure and control logistics costs, we must first make a clear and definite analysis of its composition! By analyzing the composition of logistics costs in detail, we can determine its core components and select the core indicators that are most relevant to the enterprise's strategy and goals. Logistics costs can be mainly divided into the following parts: transportation cost rate, warehousing cost rate, inventory turnover rate, processing cost rate, information management cost rate, and service cost rate.

2.2 Principal component analysis This study uses principal component analysis (PCA)

The purpose of analyzing the logistics costs of Company A is to identify key indicators that can represent the company's overall cost structure. After analysis, three main principal components were identified based on the criterion that the eigenvalue is greater than 1. The following is a detailed description and explanation of these three principal components:

PC1 (comprehensive logistics cost index): This principal component is positively correlated with transportation cost rate, warehousing cost rate, processing cost rate, information management cost rate and service cost rate, but negatively correlated with military inventory turnover rate.

PC2 (Warehousing and Information Management Efficiency Index): This principal component is positively correlated with inventory turnover rate and information management cost rate, but negatively correlated with transportation cost rate, handling cost rate, and service cost rate.

PC3 (Service and Technology Integration Index): PC3 is positively correlated with service cost rate and information management cost rate.

The principal component eigenvalues are as follows: PC1, PC2.PC3; the eigenvalues are 4.52, 1.26, and 0.67 respectively; the cumulative variance percentages are 75.30% and 96.30% respectively. 100% can obtain the following principal component matrix (see Table 2):

Table 1

Component Matrix

Cost indicators	PC1	PC2	PC3
Transportation cost rate	0.86	-0.22	0.17
Warehousing cost rate	0.88	0.2	-0.15
Inventory Turnover	-0.82	0.42	0.23
Processing cost rate	0.84	-0.27	-0.1
Information management cost rate	0.81	0.35	0.27
Service cost rate	0.79	-0.21	0.29

2.3 Results Analysis

From the above principal component analysis results, we can draw the following analysis on the logistics cost structure and characteristics of Company A:

Overall logistics cost efficiency: PC1 is the comprehensive logistics cost index with an eigenvalue of 4.52, accounting for 75.30% of the total variance, indicating that it has the highest explanation for the variation of Company A's logistics costs.

Warehousing and information management efficiency: PC2 can be interpreted as the warehousing and information management efficiency index. Its results show that Company A is lacking in the application of information technology, resulting in inefficient inventory management.

Service and technology integration: PC3 is positively correlated with the service cost rate and information management cost rate, indicating that in the process of providing better services, Company A will be accompanied by an increase in information management costs.

3. Logistics cost control strategy under supply chain management

3.1 Comprehensive Logistics Cost Optimization Strategy

The comprehensive logistics cost index (PC1) reflects the cost structure of Company A in transportation, warehousing, processing information management and services. Therefore, Company A must have a deep understanding of these areas and formulate corresponding optimization strategies. For transportation management, the use of advanced transportation management systems can achieve more efficient route planning, mode selection and time management. At the same time, establishing a stable long-term cooperative relationship with third-party logistics partners and taking advantage of economies of scale can further reduce transportation costs. The introduction of real-time transportation monitoring technology can ensure timely response to emergencies, thereby reducing additional costs caused by logistics delays. In terms of warehousing and inventory management, modern warehousing technology and automation solutions can improve warehousing efficiency and ensure that storage space is maximized. Through precise inventory management systems, such as real-time inventory tracking and predictive analysis, excess inventory can be hidden and customer needs can be met.

3.2 Warehousing and Information Management Collaborative Strategy

Based on the principal component PC2 analysis results, the close relationship between warehousing efficiency and information management capabilities is

not only the key to reducing logistics costs, but also the core link to ensure the smoothness of the supply chain. When warehousing strategies and information technology work together, the overall effectiveness of logistics operations is significantly improved. Company A should consider applying an advanced warehouse management system (WMS), which can track inventory in real time, improve storage accuracy and reduce the time of moving and searching goods. It can also communicate with other parts of the supply chain in real time to ensure inventory levels. Stay consistent with demand and avoid over-purchasing or under-stocking situations. When it comes to information management, real-time collection and analysis of data is key to developing better storage strategies. By implementing advanced logistics analytics tools, Company A can predict future inventory needs, identify potential supply chain disruptions, and plan ahead to reduce warehousing costs.

3.3 Service and technology integration and improvement strategy

From the above analysis, we can find that there is a strong correlation between services and technology, especially in the linkage between information management costs and service costs. In order to achieve higher benefits and effectively reduce costs, it is essential to strengthen the integration of services and technologies. Company A should strengthen the integration of the latest information technology into service modules, so that it can more accurately predict customer needs and process feedback in real time, thereby more effectively planning logistics. By building an integrated digital service platform, it can not only ensure that customers can easily obtain the required information at any time, such as inventory status and delivery time, but also ensure information sharing with supply chain partners, greatly improving overall collaborative efficiency and reducing response time.

CONCLUSION

In the context of globalization, logistics management capabilities have become an important part of corporate competitiveness, and logistics cost control is directly related to corporate profitability and long-term sustainability. Faced with the continued increase in supply chain complexity and the diversification of customer needs, companies are in urgent need of more efficient and flexible logistics management strategies. In this regard, this article clarifies the weight and evaluation criteria of each cost indicator by constructing a logistics cost indicator system. After conducting principal component analysis on Company A's logistics costs, the results reveal the significant impact of certain core indicators on corporate logistics cost control. . Based on the research results, this article puts forward some

targeted suggestions, hoping to provide useful reference for enterprises in logistics management practice.

References

1. Mo Yifei. Optimization analysis of logistics cost management from the perspective of supply chain [J]. *Logistics Technology*, 2024, 47(8): 104-107.
2. Wang Lingshu, Du Xinrui. Exploration and optimization of logistics cost management paths for small and medium-sized logistics enterprises, *Management and Technology of Small and Medium Enterprises*, 2023(19):80-82.
3. Li Jinxia. Logistics cost management and optimization of production enterprises based on value chain [J]. *Accounting Studies*, 2016(9):135
4. Song Min, Analysis on the optimization mechanism of enterprise logistics cost management. *China High-tech Enterprises*, 2015(17):48-49.
5. Jiang Hongmei. Optimizing logistics cost management with activity-based costing [J]. *Financial Circle*, 2010(23):50.52.
6. Yang Yan, Zhang Zhongpeng, Zeng Xianyuan. Enterprise logistics cost management and optimization based on value chain. *Sichuan, Hoisting and Transportation Machinery*, 2010(2):87-90.
7. Yin Da. Whole-process logistics cost control solution under supply chain environment [J]. *Fortune Today*, 2023(21):92-94.
8. Sun Chunming, Research on Lean Management of Logistics Cost in Hengshui No. 9 Warehouse [D]. Shijiazhuang: Hebei University of Science and Technology, 2021.
9. Chen Taiguang. Research on logistics supply chain management based on big data technology [J]. *Industrial Innovation Research*, 2023(22):44-46.
10. Li Ting, Analysis of green logistics management strategies under e-commerce environment [J]. *Shopping Mall Modernization*, 2023(23):1-3.
11. Liu Haijin. Research on warehousing and transportation optimization strategy of logistics enterprises based on virtual simulation experiment [J]. *Logistics Technology*, 2023, 46(22): 158-162+169.